

Recent Developments in Biological CO₂-Methanation in Europe and Korea

Hyunyeob Ian Yun

Wilbraham & Monson Academy

August, 2021

Abstract

According to ¹UNEP's Emissions Gap Report, Greenhouse Gas(hereinafter referred to as "GHG") emissions have risen at a rate of 1.5 per cent per year in the last decade, and total GHG emissions, including from land-use change, reached a record high of 55.3 GtCO₂e in 2018.

World Economic Forum(hereinafter referred to as WEF) has pointed out that the most challenging risk the world has been facing is the climate change and published ²"The Global Risks Report 2020", in which the climate change is clearly viewed as the most difficult task that human beings have faced.

Individual nation in the global community has been materializing the efforts to accomplish the Net-Zero of Greenhouse Gas Emission by the year of 2050, and as a primary strategy to cope with the climate change many countries implemented the progressive approaches to utilize carbon dioxide into resources as well as energy, and researched policy measures to overcome the climate change and energy problem at the same time

As a part of those efforts, the technology of Biological Methanation, which converts CO₂ into methane or major resource to generate fuel of natural gas by using microorganism, has been consistently developed

It is, therefore, meaningful to look into the outstanding cases of Europe, where the Biological Methanation technology being applied to P2G (or Power to Gas) technology, or one of energy storage technologies, as well as current trend of Korea, where CO₂ Methanation technology was recently succeeded by using microorganism.

Introduction

P2G is an innovative approach to energy storage. By converting electrical energy to chemical energy in the form of methane, the vast existing natural gas infrastructure can be leveraged for storage and transportation of renewable energy.

P2G describes the process of converting renewable energy to gaseous energy carriers such as hydrogen or methane via water electrolysis—mainly alkaline electrolysis, proton exchange

¹ United Nations Environment Programme's Emissions Gap Report 2019, <https://wedocs.unep.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.11822/30798/EGR19ESEN.pdf?sequence=13>

² World Economic Forum, "The Global Risks Report 2020" http://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Global_Risk_Report_2020.pdf

membrane (PEM) electrolysis, and solid oxide electrolysis cells (SOECs). In its most basic sense, the electrochemical process splits water into hydrogen and oxygen, and to convert it into methane, the hydrogen is reacted with carbon dioxide in the presence of catalyst.

In other word, two core technologies in P2G are water electrolysis which splits water into hydrogen and oxygen using electricity and CO₂ Methanation which combines hydrogen and carbon dioxide being generated through water electrolysis to produce methane.

*Source: KEPRI³

*Source: Power Magazine⁴

³ KEPRI,

<https://m.post.naver.com/viewer/postView.nhn?volumeNo=17862318&memberNo=41515312&searchKeyword=%EB%B0%94%EC%9D%B4%EC%98%A4%20EB%A9%94%ED%83%84%ED%99%94&searchRank=7>

According to the types of catalysts which react carbon dioxide and hydrogen, CO₂ Methanation technology could be classified into Chemical Methanation which uses nickel-based solid catalysts and Biological Methanation which uses microorganism.

Thermochemical Methanation technology maintains high operation pressure (10 bar~above) and temperature (300~550 °C), which has advantages that reaction speed is fast and the easy application of catalyst technology in other fields to existing infrastructure industries. Therefore, this characteristic enhances possibility of commercialization through early mass production.

Biological Methanation technology is one that uses methanogen as a catalyst which produces methane to react carbon dioxide with oxygen, generating high energy efficiency due to the relatively low operation pressure(0~10bar) and low temperature(20~70 °C) compared to the Thermochemical Methanation.

And this technology has high durability in perspective of low performance and shortened lifespan due to long-term operation determined by continuously increasing microorganism.

Biological Methanation technology could transform carbon dioxide, which comes from thermoelectric power plants, into methane by using the Methanogens which generates methane. Additionally, this technology could be useful to transform carbon dioxide, which was captured and stored to be abandoned in the underground and seabed previously, to the fuel for power plants, heating and cooking.

Additionally, this technology also could transform surplus power generated from new renewable energies such as solar energy or wind power energy with microorganism and carbon dioxide into methane.

Biological Methanation technology has an advantage of acquiring economic feasibility easily due to the fact that major system configuration and process such as an effector are much simpler compared to Thermochemical Methanation. Especially, this technology has been highly recognized in perspective of over system interconnection of unused electricity on the basis of renewable energy, mainly because it has high system flexibility of intermittent operation due to the characteristics of the process as well as the durability of microorganism catalyst.

⁴ Power Magazine, <https://www.powermag.com/why-power-to-gas-may-flourish-in-a-renewables-heavy-world/>

On the contrary, Biological Methanation technology could be evaluated as relatively low in its technology maturity compared to the Thermochemical Methanation. Control and optimization of operation condition for smooth microorganism reaction under the continuous operations is the most challenging task. Especially, Biological Methanation technology induces reaction by making carbon dioxide and hydrogen of gaseous state remain in the culture medium of liquid state which contains microorganism to generate methane.

In this situation, the staying length as well as solubility of the gas in the culture medium will decide the efficiency of major systems such as methane production speed and methane content.

Therefore, maintaining optimal operation conditions and monitoring on the critical elements such as ph. variation caused by the solubility deviation between carbon dioxide and hydrogen, caused by the change of the concentration and pressure of culture medium that has been influenced by the biochemical reaction of microorganisms in continuous operation, are assignments to resolve.

Source: Korea Gas Corporation⁵

Current Trend in Europe and Korea

CO₂ Methanation technologies have been mainly lead by the European countries, where Power to Gas (hereinafter referred to as “P2G”) technology development has been most actively implemented in the world.

In perspective of the whole P2G technology, around 30 plants have been operating in Europe as of now with 14 projects scheduled to initiate soon. Approximately, 70% of those projects are producing hydrogen products and 30% of those projects are producing methane products as final

⁵ Korea Gas Corporation,
<https://m.post.naver.com/viewer/postView.nhn?volumeNo=25877945&memberNo=6411495&vType=VERTICAL>

ones, and it is investigated that in perspective of plant sizes plants more than 1MW are 36%, those between 100KW and 1MW are 34% and those less than 100KW are 30% respectively.

In implementing projects on methanation of carbon dioxide, Thermal Chemical Methanation Technology and Biological Methanation Technology are being applied proportionally, and recently researches on Biological Methanation Technology related to bioplant industries, which have well-prepared infrastructures on microorganism, have been increased gradually.

Regarding researches on Biological Methanation technology, Bio-Cat⁶ project of German Electrochaea corporation is a fairly representative one. Electrochaea corporation has considerably advanced technologies in Biological Methanation sector and these relevant projects are empirical studies on Biological Methanation based on P2G technology, which has been widely applied to Biological Methanation Empirical Plants inked with renewable energy of 1MW in avendore region of Demark.

In Electrochaea's biological methanation system, approximately 150 tons of hydrogen are produced annually using the alkaline electrolyzer technology. And those hydrogen produced would bring out methane using Biological Methanation with reaction of carbon dioxide generated from biogas plants. Moreover, It is aimed that those produced methane would be directly connected with City Gas Distribution Pipeline which would be directly utilized for the City Gas fuels.

In Electrochaea's biological methanation system, the hydrogen from the electrolyzer is combined with carbon dioxide, and this gas mixture is then introduced to a liquid phase methanation reactor. Over the course of the experimental testing phase in the BioCat Project, two sources of carbon dioxide will be used: (i) raw biogas from an adjacent anaerobic digester with a composition of approximately 60% methane and 40% carbon dioxide, and (ii) a pure stream of CO₂ supplied by an on-site biogas upgrading system.

Inside the bioreactor, a culture of methanogenic archaea metabolizes the hydrogen and carbon dioxide to methane. Archaea are single-celled organisms (prokaryotes) that have evolved over billions of years in harsh environments. The specific strain used by Electrochaea's methanation system has been selectively evolved (not genetically modified) in the laboratory of Prof. Laurens Mets at the University of Chicago and exhibits properties ideal for applications in industrial environments. Those properties include:

⁶ BioCat Project : <http://biocat-project.com/>

- Low energy metabolic pathway from carbon dioxide to methane
- Very high carbon mass conversion efficiency
- High tolerance to contamination (oxygen, hydrogen sulfide, particulates)
- Moderate operating temperatures (60-65°C)
- High selectivity in product gas (100% methane, no intermediate products)
- Low catalyst operating costs enabled by self-maintenance and self-replication
- Very high responsiveness (ability to cycle on/off within seconds)

Denmark is aiming at procuring 80% of its total power consumption from domestic wind energy by 2050. Due to this challenging renewables target, the country has taken a position to be forefront of the energy transition.

To keep the balance between supply and demand in the power grid all the time, any excess electricity is exported to other countries or stored in Denmark for later use. Denmark uses its P2G infrastructure to store renewable energy in an unlimited manner. P2G is a novel production route for renewable gas that can be used in transportation and heating applications.

Denmark's ambitious renewable targets have led to the development and early deployment of the P2G technology.

Qvidja Kraft in Finland was established in 2015, which has developed the production process of Biological Methanation based on P2G and climate change. In implementing Biological Methanation production process, this company has a characteristic that its Biological Methanation production process was developed under the solid state unlike Methanation production process using the culture medium as previously reported.

Previous culturing method in liquid needs the pressure under 10 bars, while the Qvidja Kraft methanation doesn't need to increase the pressure, which eventually has an advantage that relatively high energy efficiency and relatively simple reaction system are possibly established.

There is a huge distinction that *Electrochaea* uses pure strains for methanation while Qvidja Kraft uses mixed microorganism for methanation. In the projects where Qvidja Kraft has been carrying out Biological Methanation has been carried out with biogas and syngas all for resources, and installed and operated Biological Methanation system in Qvidja region.

*Source : Quidja Kraft⁷

Solid state biomethanation (Quidja Kraft technology) vs. other technologies

Parameter	Chemical	Biological liquid fermentation	Biological solid state (Quidja Kraft)	Quidja Kraft advantage
Conversion	chemical	biological, pure culture	biological, mixed culture	Higher stability
Operation temperature	300-400°C	60-65°C	50-55°C	Lower temperature
Operation pressure	high pressure	pressure is used and mixing	no pressure or mixing used	Lower pressure
Tolerance against contamination	low	High	high	Raw biogas can be used a CO₂ source
Product gas	CH ₄ + side products	CH ₄	CH ₄	No upgrading required
Product purity	~92%	98-99%	98-99%	No product purification required
Energy efficiency	~50%	58%	~78-80%	Lower operating costs
System complexity	high	medium	low	Lower capital costs, higher flexibility based on modules

*Source : Quidja Kraft⁸

KEPCO Research Institute (hereinafter referred to as “KEPRI”), or a Research and Development Center of Korea Electric Power Corporation (KEPCO), which has jointly co-worked with Techross Water and Energy Incorporation and the Hanyang University, has mainly led a research on carbon dioxide Methanation using microorganism in Korea,.

⁷ Quidja Kraft, http://www.sae.gov.ua/sites/default/files/Alitalo_NBB17.pdf

⁸ Quidja Kraft, http://www.sae.gov.ua/sites/default/files/Alitalo_NBB17.pdf

In this project, they produced hydrogen using unused electricity caused by the expansion of reusable energy. And the hydrogen is reacted with carbon dioxide, which was collected in a power plant or a bioplant, will be transformed into methane to be utilized for town gas and transportation fuel. In transforming process, they aim to obtain essential technologies in related Biological Methanation such as microorganism culturing and collecting technology, process design and system operation technology

In January 2020, KEPCO Research Institute, or KEPRI has developed technology that transforms carbon dioxide, or greenhouse gas, into methane using microorganism for the first time in Korea. And it set up a 5kw testbed facility which utilized 36 tons of carbon dioxide annually to produce 12 tons of methane.

KEPRI independently developed two sets of new microorganism, which is reported for the first time in the world with the efficiency of methane production as high as 1.7 times. This microorganism consumes carbon dioxide and hydrogen to produce methane and expel it while increasing methane production by giving low electricity to microorganism.

It is a very critical issue in perspective of commercialization whether KEPRI exclusively obtains the essential patents in Methanation using independently developed microorganisms. If using microorganism that other foreign advanced research institutions possessed for commercializing Methanation technology of biological carbon dioxide it is required to receive the permission in advance from the country to which the research institutes obtaining the concerned microorganisms belong according to the Nagoya Protocol. Additionally, it is required to review the economical inefficiency when sharing the research products and their profits from the commercialization of these microorganisms.

Therefore, independently obtaining methanization microorganism and intellectual property of relevant processing technologies would greatly contribute to resolving the issue of securing profitability in commercialization stage.

*Source: KEPRI⁹

Korea Electric Power Corporation secured several technologies such as selecting methanation microorganisms, mass propagation and methane production plants to convert large quantity of carbon dioxide into methane gas. Moreover, this corporation will conduct technology assessment through demonstration facilities of 1MW capacity by the year of 2022 while developing and distributing stand-by facilities of 50 MW capacity after the year of 2023.

Substitution effect of fuel expenses as much as 50 million USD annually are expected if daily converting carbon dioxide of 1000 tons into methane through stand-by facility of 50 MW capacities and using them for generating fuels of natural gas.

In Korea, as new renewable energy is expected to expand it is urgently required to develop the Energy Storing System to back up the fluctuation of solar powers and wind powers to stabilize electricity supply. KEPRI has developed technologies for converting into green methane, which possibly stores large quantity of energy for long periods, by combining hydrogen from the reproduced electricity and carbon dioxide collected from thermoelectric power plants.

Thanks to those technologies, they easily take advantages of them for P2G Energy Storing Devices, where they reserve and use electricity whenever necessary, which eventually makes the outputs of wind powers and solar powers more stable, since they have changed every moment due to weather conditions such as wind, cloud and so on.

⁹ KEPRI, <https://m.post.naver.com/viewer/postView.nhn?volumeNo=17862318&memberNo=41515312&searchKeyword=%EB%B0%94%EC%9D%B4%EC%98%A4%20EB%A9%94%ED%83%84%ED%99%94&searchRank=7>

*Source: KEPRI¹⁰

4. Conclusion

Individual nation in the global community has strived out to activate the supply of renewable energy for reducing greenhouse gas as well as for converting its relevant policy into new energy environment. There might be a difference of speed, though it is clear that we have to acknowledge that supply and spread of renewable energy is inevitable and essential.

European countries as well as California in US set goals that 50% of electricity would be supplied with renewable energy and 30 % of transportation fuels would be substituted with Renewable Natural Gas (RNG) methane produced from recycled energy by year of 2030. Meanwhile, Japan also sets a goal to increase the portion of renewable energy production upto 22-24% by year of 2030.

As the efforts to spread the supply of renewable energy have enhanced the diverse measures to stabilize electricity supply networks and to efficiently utilize the renewable energy are ultimately required. In this regard, technology of Power to Gas could be an option to prepare for the measures.

¹⁰KEPRI,

<https://m.post.naver.com/viewer/postView.nhn?volumeNo=26792195&memberNo=41515312&searchKeyword=%EB%B0%94%EC%9D%B4%EC%98%A4%20%E B%A9%94%ED%83%84%ED%99%94&searchRank=5>

Biological Methanation technology is still relatively immature in perspective of technology maturity compared to thermal chemical Methanation. However, taking into account that this technology has an advantage that energy efficiency is relatively high as well as cost for constructing facility is pretty low it is strongly recommended to make more efforts in achieving technological breakthroughs for commercialization and universalization.